

GO-GRASS Training Kit

Realise your rural vision!

Discover our digital tools for your successful grass-based business and beyond.

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Welcome to the GO-GRASS Training Kit!

The GO-GRASS project is dedicated to creating small-scale bio-based solutions that not only transform grassland landscapes but also generate new business opportunities for rural areas.

What's inside:

In this Training Kit, you will find a collection of factsheets introducing the various tools developed as part of the GO-GRASS project. Whether you are a rural entrepreneur, municipality representative, stakeholder, or trainer, these tools are tailored to guide you through exploring, understanding, and replicating the circular grass-based business models developed by the GO-GRASS consortium.

Our goal is to help you understand how to make the most of grasslands in a way that benefits both the environment and local economies.

Turn the page
and **explore!**

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Online Business Plan Writer

For **Entrepreneurs**
and **Advisors**

Description

This online tool provides a clear framework to cover all important aspects of a business model. The entrepreneur will be able to convert a conceptual business idea into a comprehensive business plan by working through all of the tool's sections, as well as evaluating the viability and credibility of the business strategy. There are three features of the tool supporting the creation of a business plan:

1. Writing module: ensures that the business model has a narrative and that all relevant areas are thoroughly explained in written text.
2. Budget module: strengthens the financial background of the business plan and as a result, secures that the visions and assumptions are converted into monetary terms.
3. Evaluation module: allows the plan to be sent for professional business evaluation.

The content and structure of the writing module include findings from real-life cases and relevant business theories.

How to use the tool

The Online Business Plan Writer tool offers a user-friendly web platform for creating business plans. After registration, you can start working on your business plan which is organised into five sections for a manageable step-by-step process. The five sections and the connecting elements are designed to cover key aspects for investors or grant applications. The tool features a structure that combines theory and practice. Each section has a brief description and supporting illustrations to guide your writing. Associated financial analyses (Profits and Loss, Balance Sheets, and Liquidity) are automatically calculated based on your input. Once all relevant sections are completed, the business plan is ready for evaluation!

Writing module: The five sections

Budget module: Results and graphs

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How to Get Started and Succeed Manual

For **Trainers**
and **Entrepreneurs**

Description

Business ideas start in various ways, but the steps to turn them into real ventures share common aspects. We've narrowed down these common elements into five key parts. These are:

1. Business model
2. Market and customers
3. Product and production
4. Management
5. Budget and financials

How deep you go into each part depends on what you're interested in and what your business needs. These topics need to be addressed with different levels of depth depending on the individual user's interests and needs. Addressing these five elements establishes a robust foundation for developing a comprehensive, case-focused business strategy or plan.

How to use the tool

The manual gives a comprehensive overview of the different elements and their connection in converting ideas to successful businesses. After the description of each main category, actionable items are listed, summarising the key learnings and listing specific steps to be done. The manual aims to primarily support current and future entrepreneurs, however regional representatives and end-user networks can use the manual to provide tailor-made advice on how to turn innovative business ideas into concrete business plans. The last chapter refers to additional tools and resources that can support the planning process.

The five pillars of business plan creation

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MR

Master Class Modules

For Trainers
and Regional Representatives

Description

This tool aids trainers and regional representatives in guiding rural entrepreneurs through essential business planning steps. The Master Class Modules, structured in alignment with the Online Business Plan Writer tool and How to Get Started and Succeed Manual, cover the five key areas of business planning. Each area is presented through a set of unique slides, focusing on specific business topics. These presentation-ready modules allow trainers to seamlessly integrate them into events or discussions with stakeholders. Collaboratively developed with GO-GRASS partners, researchers, and bioeconomy experts, the slides feature real-life examples from developments in the project. This ensures trainers have sector-specific examples readily available, helping participants grasp how business decisions connect to the bioeconomy sector.

How to use the tool

Each of the five sets of presentation slide decks consists of 20-35 slides, designed to be presented in half an hour by a trainer. Divided into five separate presentations, it's flexible—trainers can pick and choose relevant topics for events or combine them as needed. Alternatively, they can present all slide decks in a workshop to cover all main business planning areas.

If needed, we recommend reviewing the detailed How to Get Started and Succeed Manual before presenting, as it provides in-depth knowledge on the topics covered in the presentations, helping trainers prepare in advance.

The presentations are in PDF format and can be found on the GO-GRASS website under the Training tab.

Five modules:

- 1 Business model, sales & marketing partners
- 2 Customers, customer needs and market
- 3 Product, customer, production and key resources
- 4 Management, IPR and administration
- 5 Budget, funding and investors

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Train the Trainer scheme

For **Trainers** , **Intermediaries** and **Multipliers**

Description

The tool serves as a comprehensive guide within the GO-GRASS project, offering insights into relevant tools, their applications, and a suggested training timeline. Its primary aim is to empower trainers to effectively utilise GO-GRASS resources and replicate project results for entrepreneurs in their local context.

The document presents a structured overview of the tools developed in the GO-GRASS project, highlighting their specifics, unique characteristics, suggested use and validation. Trainers have the flexibility to select the tools that best align with their training purpose. The tool guides trainers in leveraging GO-GRASS results for the benefit of entrepreneurs. The scenario featured in the last chapter offers inspiration for effective training session planning.

Available
for
GO-GRASS
partners
only

How to use the tool

Trainers can dive into the individual tools using the Train the Trainer scheme as a roadmap, detailing steps for using GO-GRASS tools. A tool guide with overviews, descriptions, and values aids trainers in understanding and implementing each tool effectively. The document also outlines the role and expectations of the trainer, introduces learning styles for adults and provides a frame on how to plan training sessions.

This tool is defined as a confidential deliverable in the GO-GRASS project and is available to partners of the project in a PDF format.

A practical guide
to setting up
training sessions
and integrating
relevant tools from
the GO-GRASS
project.

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Method and Evaluation Sheet to compare business cases

For **Mentors** , **Entrepreneurs**
and **Authorities**

Description

The purpose of the tool is to give entrepreneurs interested in replicating GO-GRASS business models feedback on their capacities. The tool consists of a series of questions related to the capacity of their business and the requirements to replicate one of the business models. This score serves as a valuable metric for entrepreneurs to evaluate their preparedness and get an overview of the additional requirements for successful replication. The tool offers a quick overview, allowing entrepreneurs to make informed decisions before committing significant time and resources to the replication process.

TOOL

How to use the tool

The tool is an Excel spreadsheet. Users should simply click on their response to each question and the result will be a weighted score based on the importance of each question.

After completing the questions, the result is a final score, which is obtained from a matrix that converts the qualitative response into a quantitative one based on the importance of each category in the overall assessment of their capacities. The questions are weighted based on the model of Orozco and Grundmann (2022)¹ depending on their category: experience/business readiness, staff capabilities/team readiness, and resources/manufacturing readiness.

Replication simplified:

Click , Assess , and Score your potential

¹Orozco, R.; Grundmann, P. Readiness for Innovation of Emerging Grass-Based Businesses. J. Open Innov. Technol. Mark. Complex. 2022, 8, 180.

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Business Environment Support Tool

Guidelines for creating supportive framework conditions for rural innovations

For **Replicators**
and **Entrepreneurs**

Description

The aim of the tool is to develop measures and solutions to overcome gaps and obstacles that enterprises are confronted with in their business environment.

There are two main features unique to the tool. Firstly, a survey is used to assess the level of support and identify the gaps in the business environment according to seven sub-arenas: technology and knowledge, resources and infrastructure, consumer agency, market structure, training and education, funding and institutional development.

Secondly, based on the first-hand information collected, the tool provides a manual and material for conducting an online workshop on the development of the business environment. This workshop tool is designed to help actors identify and agree on strategy implementation, formulate local and targeted activities and mobilise capacity to implement the solutions developed for the business environment.

How to use the tool

The survey is carried out before the workshop by the workshop organisers. The purpose of the survey is to have a first overview of the state of support of the business environments from the perspective of the workshop participants. At the start of the workshop, the participants can see the results in the slides of the workshop presentation. The organisers can choose which relevant results to choose to ignite interest and kick-start the discussions.

In summary, Stage 1 involves a diverse survey to map gaps in seven business sub-arenas, with results available via a Google Forms link (A).

In Stage 2, a workshop presents survey findings to facilitate discussions among stakeholders.

Stage 3 focuses on developing strategies for more supportive business environments, detailed in a PDF at rubizmo.eu (B).

The GO-GRASS project developed an online version of the tool with an additional extension using a MURAL App for the joint and interactive formulation, visualisation and documentation of gaps, strategies, measures and actions.

In this way, the actors involved can follow the flow of ideas in real time and interactively shape the design of solution measures. The results of the tool are digitised and the findings can always be revisited and used for further development activities.

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Online Decision Support Tool for flexible integration of value chain components

For **Agri-food Consultants**,
Trainers and **Intermediaries**

Description

The goal of the Online Decision Support Tool is to help agricultural advisors make more informed decisions about a business idea related to the processing of grass.

The tool offers insights about critical factors and best practices, based on the four GO-GRASS demonstration sites and possible value chains for grassland valorisation. The focus is on the processing, scaling up, and technologies for grass valorisation.

The tool showcases best practices and opportunities to create grass-based value chains and sustainable grass products and provides recommendations according to the user's conditions (biomass, logistics, market, technology and knowledge).

How to use the tool

The tool consists of an online web platform and a user manual. It offers tailored guidance by providing information about critical factors, based on the four GO-GRASS demonstration sites' scenarios and additional optimal scenarios for grassland valorisation. The critical factors represent requirements that need to be considered when assessing the potential of innovative grass-based value chains, such as the availability and access to grass and infrastructures, consumers' perceptions and capacity development. The optimal scenarios are ways to improve the current value chains developed by the four demonstration sites, by combining different components from each demonstration site and using the value chains side streams.

After selecting the product you aim to develop using grass, the platform will take you to a short questionnaire with five main categories. The completion of the questions will result in a viability assessment according to one of the seven pre-fixed scenarios, tailor-made recommendations and inspiring best practices.

Best practices & opportunities in three steps

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Interactive maps to access resources

For **Grass-based Businesses**, **Researchers**
and **Rural Development Agencies**

Description

The user-friendly interactive maps of Europe display a wide range of data and GO-GRASS resources, such as:

- Key data about grassland type and availability
- Users can explore the potential of grass-based business models in their regions and the state of development of the biobased sectors in their countries
- Users can find new relevant partners (GO-GRASS partners, universities, feed companies, organic farmers, process equipment, etc)

Through a short form, grass-based businesses and entrepreneurs can upload their data (address, name of the company, website, services and products, type of grass/raw materials) and be visible on the stakeholders' map.

The uniqueness of the tool lies in transforming complex grassland data in an easy-to-use way and thus helping business assess their viability with grass-based ideas.

How to use the tool

On the online **interactive maps**, you can get access to data about grassland type and availability, socio-economic conditions, and livestock across Europe and explore the potential of grass-based business models in your region and your country.

On the **stakeholder map**, users can find their next partners and discover innovative grass-based businesses. The type of stakeholders is colour-coded and placed on the map. By clicking on the stakeholder, you can see additional information, such as website and address.

DISPLAY MY COMPANY ON THE MAP

Title *

Category *

What kind of stakeholder are you?

Other Stakeholder

Services or products

Details about your work in 1000 characters.

Website

Optional URL to your website.

Location *

If you have no precise address, point to a town center.

Search for address.

Map Satellite

Terrain

SUBMIT YOUR STAKEHOLDER REQUEST

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noa

The green voyage: The hidden potential of grass

For **General Public**

Description

The purpose of the tool is to raise awareness about the importance of grassland among the general public, as well as to gather real-time information on how newly developed grass products are perceived by the potential end-users.

The tool will anonymously gather and analyse all information given by the consumers who take part in the virtual tool and provide this information to the GO-GRASS demo partners as an additional source to help them better understand the current customer expectations. Apart from that, the analysis of the answers will provide an insight into the level of awareness regarding the importance of grassland among the general public.

After the end of the project, this information will be available to researchers and other interested parties on the Prospex Institute website.

How to use the tool

The tool is available in the form of an online site and upon entering, the visitors are given a short introduction to the topic followed by a series of questions divided into three sections.

The first section is in the form of a quiz, where users are asked to choose from a number of answers per question to test their level of knowledge and awareness about the importance of grassland.

In the second section, the users are asked to provide their honest perspectives on more sustainable products and their potential usage, as well as to answer a few demographic questions.

The third section is divided into 4 subsections following the GO-GRASS demonstration sites, namely the roadside grass paper, the grass biochar, the grass protein and the grass animal bedding, among which the users are able to choose freely.

From awareness to action:

Engage, learn and
shape the future
of grassland!

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THANK YOU

... for being a part of the GO-GRASS journey! By using these tools, you are not only shaping your own success but also contributing to a more sustainable and resilient future for grassland communities across Europe.

Acknowledgement

As we conclude this Training Kit, we extend our sincere appreciation to the partners, collaborators, and contributors who have played an integral role in the development of these tools. Their dedication to sustainable bio-based solutions is the driving force behind the success of the GO-GRASS project.

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Discover more

